

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

IMPROVING COLORECTAL CANCER SCREENING IN PRIMARY CARE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Panujee Bijayayothin

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Annie Odell, PhD, RN, FNP, Team Leader
Gayle Early, PhD, RN, FNP-BC, Team Member

May 2019

Copyright Panujee Bijayayothin 2019 ©

ABSTRACT

Early detection of colorectal cancer (CRC) can be done efficiently by providing a referral for a colonoscopy, fecal immunochemical, or guaiac fecal occult blood kits. In the United States, the National Colorectal Cancer Roundtable (NCCRT) estimated that if providers achieved CRC screening of 80% of the target population by 2018, over 200,000 lives would be saved. Previously, providers only screened about one-third of the targeted patients on average. This was the impetus for the development of a quality improvement (QI) program by the Center of Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS). As a result, the CMS provides “bonus” reimbursements to clinics meeting the 80% criteria. Starting in 2008, the Medicare Star-Rating Program (MSRP) began tracking primary care clinics’ screening performance according to payors. While demonstrating some success, there were minimal data to explain why other clinics do not achieve recommended scores with their CRC screening. This Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was designed to increase CRC screening performance levels in a busy Los Angeles primary care practice clinic that has never made baseline scores. The Teamlet Training Pathway (TTP) was used to implement the process with the staff, providers, and patients. Improving provider, staff, and patient education increased the clinic’s CRC screening by more than 10%. The Health Belief Model (HBM) was used to inform whether the interventions changed the clinic staff and providers’ behaviors. The results of this project indicate that the HBM

and TTP could be effective methods to improve CRC screening in certain outpatient clinics.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	v
LIST OF TABLES.....	ix
LIST OF FIGURES	x
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	xi
BACKGROUND	1
Problem Statement.....	1
Purpose Statement.....	2
Supporting Framework	2
The Health Belief Model (HBM).....	3
The Teamlet Model (TM).....	4
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	6
Overview.....	6
CRC Screening Guidelines	7
Barriers to CRC Screening by Providers	10
Barriers to CRC Screening by Patients.....	11
Intervention to Improve CRC Screening	12
The Medicare Star-Rating and Provider Incentive Programs.....	14
METHODS	16
Setting.....	16
Sample	16
Measures	17
Procedures.....	17
Timeline.....	20
Ethical Issues	21
RESULTS	22

DISCUSSION	29
Limitations	30
Recommendation for Practice.....	30
REFERENCES	31
APPENDIX A: IRB ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	39
APPENDIX B: PHYSICIAN-OWNER APPROVAL	42
APPENDIX C: CRC MATERIALS FOR PATIENTS	43
APPENDIX D: SAMPLE KNOWLEDGE QUIZ FOR STAFF AND PROVIDERS	45
APPENDIX E: TABLE OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL	46

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Initial Search Strategies	17
2. Exclusion Diagnoses and ICD-10 Codes.....	27
3. Project Timeline.....	32
4. Numbers of Patients who Received CRC Screening During Data Collection	36

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Health Belief Model.....	15
2. Health Belief Model and Teamlet Training Pathway	31
3. Patients who were seen during the time of implementation with review of CRC screening documentation and different payor coverages.....	34
4. Race/ethnicity of patients who received CRC screening orders during the project implementation	35
5. Medical Group A results on CRC screening from March through December 2018.....	38
6. Medical Group B results on CRC screening from July 2018 to January 2019....	38

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to express my deepest appreciation to my lead chair committee, Dr. Annie Odell, for her time, expertise, assistance, guidance, and patience during the process of writing this project. I am very grateful to Dr. Gayle Early and Dr. Margaret Brady for helping me in this process. I am deeply indebted to Shayna Litvin for her friendship and support. I appreciate the Los Angeles clinic for allowing me to do this project and to work with its staff and providers.

A special thank you to my grandparents, my husband, and my two loving daughters, for always lifting up my spirit, helping me focus, loving me unconditionally, and encouraging me to accomplish my goal. I love you guys with all my heart and this project is dedicated to you.

BACKGROUND

According to the American Cancer Society [ACS] (2018) cancer care costs in the United States were estimated to be \$80.2 billion in 2015. Regular health screenings can detect many types of cancer in their early stages and can also lead to early treatment (Meester et al., 2015). Primary care providers (PCPs) account for most of the evidence-based chronic disease prevention and screening services. PCPs are expected to provide non-invasive colorectal cancer (CRC) screening tests. These tests are simple and effective for screening patients who may not qualify or be willing to have invasive procedures. However, there continues to be a gap between recommended preventive services and what is done in practice. The reasons for this gap are not well understood. However, recent studies suggest providers found available time to be a barrier to meet the recommended screening guidelines (Grunfeld et al., 2013).

CRC is the second leading cause of cancer-related death, and the third most common cancer in both males and females in the United States (CDC, 2017). The American Cancer Society [ACS] (2018) estimated that by 2018, 97,220 new cases of colon cancer and 43,030 cases of rectal cancer would be diagnosed. The 5-year survival rate in stage II versus stage IV is 92% and 12% respectively. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC] (2017) identified in 2014, 139,992 people were diagnosed with CRC in the United States, with a five-year mortality rate of about 37%.

Problem Statement

The setting for this project was a primary care clinic located in an urban area of Los Angeles (LA) County and is referred to as the “clinic” for this paper. The clinic serves an ethnically diverse population, with the vast majority of patients aged 50 and

older. On reviewing the clinic's performance, the clinic CRC screening scores had the lowest rating for quality measure; earning only one star out of five. An employed nurse practitioner (NP) independently promoted CRC screening and as result, the CRC screening score improved from 38 % to 50%. Conversely, when the NP stopped working at the clinic, the screening rates decreased. Therefore, this DNP project aimed to: identify barriers for improving its CRC screening outcomes, implement interventions using the Teamlet Model (TM), and using the HBM to measure provider, staff, and patient behavior changes.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to evaluate the effectiveness of utilizing the Health Belief Model (HBM) and the Teamlet Model (TM) on CRC screening scores. The project involved the clinic staff, providers, and patients age 50 to 75 years. The specific goals for this project included:

1. Provided the structure for implementing the TM and current CRC screening practices in the clinic
2. Evaluated the effectiveness of the HBM and CRC screening rates in the selected clinic

Supporting Framework

The aim of this project is to increase the overall CRC screening rate in the clinic to five stars by using evidence-based activities. Two frameworks, the TM and HBM, were employed to promote and evaluate the effects of both models on CRC screening rates.

The Health Belief Model (HBM)

In the 1950s, social psychologists Hochbaum, Rosenstock, and Kegels initially developed the HBM to improve health-screening behaviors for public health. Karls and Cobb (1965) defined health behaviors as “any activity undertaken by a person who believes himself to be healthy, for the purpose of preventing disease or detecting disease in an asymptomatic stage” (as cited in Rosenstock, 2005, p. 2). The model was first used to increase tuberculosis screening. Later, it was applied to study behaviors associated with the prevention or detection of numerous diseases (University of Twente, 2017).

Carpenter (2010) described the HBM as six components including perceived susceptibility; perceived seriousness or severity; perceived benefits; perceived barriers; cue to action, and self- efficacy. A person’s perception of each of these components predict the likelihood of their willingness to comply with healthier behaviors. Using the HBM as the framework for CRC screening programs has been identified in several studies (Wools, Dapper, & Leeuw, 2016).

The reason to use the HBM is to affect the perceptions of the providers and their staff (Peterson et al., 2016; Weiss et al., 2017). Because this is a physician owned clinic, he would need to see the benefits of using the HBM to his clinic and patients before he would be willing to make permanent practice changes. The HBM included measuring the clinic’s staff as well as the other providers’ behaviors. By doing so, barriers could be identified and ultimately would increase CRC screenings and CRC referral rates. The application of the HBM for the clinic’s staff and providers required a plan for ongoing reinforcement of the importance and benefits of CRC screenings. Also, the clinic needed

an educational program to continue to ensure that staff and providers were educated about the risks of not properly screening patients (Figure 1).

The Teamlet Model (TM)

Bodenheimer and Laing (2007) suggested that primary care providers usually spend an average of 15 minutes with each patient. They reported that 15 minutes is inadequate to deliver messages about important services expected. Therefore, without additional time, patients may leave not fully understanding of what they were told by providers. This could result in a lack of shared decision-making between patients and providers (Bodenheimer & Laing, 2007; Mosen et al., 2013).

The TM or “little team,” as shown in Figure 2, is designed to go beyond and enhance the usual 15-minute visit at the primary care office. It consists of one provider and two health coaches. The original TM has two features: 1) patients encounter two healthcare providers (one clinician and one health coach); 2) the 15-minute extended visit includes pre-visit, visit, after a visit, and between visits (Bodenheimer & Laing, 2007). The model includes training medical assistants (MAs) as the health coaches and would facilitate the recommendations of the providers (Bodenheimer & Laing, 2007; Ngo, Hammer, & Bodenheimer, 2010). In order to incorporate the two frameworks, the Teamlet Training Pathway (TTP) was created as the CRC screening process for the selected clinic.

Figure 1. The Health Belief Model application to providers and staff perceptions on CRC screening.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

A comprehensive review of the literature (ROL) utilized electrical databases, including CINAHL and PubMed. Search terms included “colorectal cancer screening guidelines,” “barriers to colorectal cancer screening,” “barriers to colorectal screening by providers,” “interventions to improve CRC screening,” and “Medicare Star-Rating Program.” The limiters of the search were English-language articles published between 2013 and 2018. Most articles selected were mostly peer-reviewed. The reference lists of retrieved articles were explored for additional relevancy. The ROL was separated into five subtopics: CRC screening guidelines, barriers to CRC screening by providers, barriers to CRC screening, interventions to improve CRC screening, and the Medicare Star-Rating and Provider Incentive Program as shown in Table 1. Within the subtopics, the main ideas were extracted from the search. The main focus was the CRC screening guidelines as provided by the U.S. Preventative Services Task Force (USPSTF) and the ACS. For barriers to CRC screening for patients and providers, the concentration was on cultures and behaviors. Interventions to improve CRC screening were emphasized using education and outreach. Lastly, the Medicare Star-Rating and Provider Incentive Program was focused on incentives and reimbursement from preventative health screening such as CRC screening.

Table 1

Initial Search Strategy

Topic	Search Terms	# Found	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
CRC Screening Guidelines	Colorectal cancer screening guidelines	PubMed = 127	21	7
		CINAHL = 14	14	1
Barriers to CRC Screening	Barriers to colorectal cancer screening	PubMed = 76	15	3
		CINAHL = 7	7	1
Barriers to CRC Screening by Providers	Barriers to colorectal cancer screening by providers	PubMed = 92	20	0
		CINAHL = 3,522	20	4
Intervention to Improve CRC Screening	Improve colorectal cancer screening	PubMed = 325	30	3
		CINAHL = 8	8	1
The Medicare Star-Rating and Provider Incentive Programs	Medicare star-rating	PubMed = 83	5	2
		CINAHL = 8	8	0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to the project topic.

CRC Screening Guidelines

The ACS (2018) defined CRC as cancer that initiates in the colon or the rectum not including the anus or small intestine. Cancer can either be called colon cancer or rectal cancer depending on where it starts. They may be grouped according to the similarity of their features (ACS, 2018). The majority of CRC arise from polyps, which are growths on the inner lining of colon or rectum. There are two types of polyps including adenomatous polyps (pre-cancerous) and hyperplastic polyps and inflammatory polyps (non-cancerous). Other indications for polyps that could become cancerous include: one that is larger than 1 cm, when more than two polyps are found, and dysplasia is seen after the removal (ACS, 2018).

CRC screenings tests include: 1) stool testing (mainly to detect cancer) such as guaiac-based fecal occult blood tests (gFOBTs), immunochemical-based fecal occult blood tests (FITs), and stool tests for exfoliated DNA (sDNA) and 2) invasive tests that can detect cancer and advanced lesions (e.g. colonoscopy, flexible sigmoidoscopy (SIG), and radiological examination such as double-contrast barium enema and computed tomography colonography (CTC) (Smith et al., 2015; USPSTF, 2016).

The USPSTF's updated recommendations for CRC screening suggested: 1) an A recommendation (substantially beneficial) for CRC screening via SIG, colonoscopy, and FOBT beginning at age 50 until age 75 years, 2) a C recommendation (benefit small or moderate) for selective screening in adults ages 76 to 85, and 3) a D recommendation (no benefit and/or harm outweigh benefit) for screening patients above the age of 85 years (USPSTF, 2016). The USPSTF (2016) recommends a standard screening for asymptomatic adults 50 to 75 years of age with average risk of CRC getting a colonoscopy every 10 years, SIG with FIT or gFOBT every five years, and gFOBT or FIT every year. Intervals for repeating the CRC screening tests depend on risk factors for CRC of each individual. Those risks include personal or family history of CRC or adenomas, high-risk conditions such as inflammatory bowel diseases (IBDs), familial adenomatous polyposis, or Lynch syndrome (Smith et al., 2017). Though gender and race are not included in the risk assessment recommendation, the clinicians should be aware that certain populations are more prone to CRC than others, such as African American males (Bromley, May, Federer, Spiegel, & Van Oijen, 2015; Carethers, 2014; USPSTF, 2016).

Reviewing the most current and accurate evidence is crucial for a clinician to determine the benefits and risks of each CRC testing method. Manser et al. (2012) suggested that a single colonoscopy with possible polypectomy is one of the most efficient tools for CRC screening due to the significant improvement in CRC reduction and prevention. Although previous retrospective data questioned the effectiveness of colonoscopy in assessing the entire colon for CRC, this study demonstrated that colonoscopy was adequate (Manser et al., 2012). However, colonoscopies are more invasive than other tests, thereby increasing risks from procedural complications up to and including major bleeding or bowel perforations (Lin, et al. 2016; USPSTF, 2016). On the other hand, CTC is able to adequately detect CRC; however, its dangers include exposure to low-dose radiation as well as the potential discovery of findings outside of the colon, which occur in approximately 40 to 70% of screening tests (Lin et al., 2016). The literature about the harms of CTC is still in the novice stage, yet CTC remains a back-up choice with strict criteria and is reserved for those with contraindications to colonoscopy (Lin et al., 2016; USPSTF, 2016).

Holme et al.'s (2014) randomized control trial (RCT) proposed that the use of SIG has the potential to be more cost effective in screening patients for CRC than colonoscopy. However, proximal adenomas in the colon could be missed due to the limited range of SIG, leading to missed diagnoses of CRC (Holme et al., 2014; Lin et al., 2016). Another RCT supports the current practice of at-home gFOBTs. The authors claimed that mailing gFOBT kits to screen for CRC is a feasible intervention in a population-based healthcare delivery setting. They recommended that clinicians consider the potential higher uptake of FIT over gFOBT (Chubak, Bogart, Fuller, Laing, & Green,

2013; Smith et al., 2017). The appropriateness of stool tests also depends on whether patients could adhere to the annual testing (Lin et al., 2016; USPSTF, 2016). Clinicians should also consider that individual patients might prefer some methods of CRC over others. For instance, a colonoscopy needs time commitment from the patient for prepping, procedure, and recovery. The advantage of CTC is that the need for repeat procedures have longer intervals (usually five to 10 years) between screenings in comparison to stool tests (USPSTF, 2016). This project emphasizes two screening tests, stool testing and colonoscopy.

Barriers to CRC Screening by Providers

Primary care providers (PCPs) play major roles in the CRC screening process and their performances in CRC screening can be based on multiple factors. PCPs perceptions of CRC screening correlated with their behaviors to screen patients for CRC (Peterson et al., 2016; Weiss et al., 2017). PCPs who perceive major barriers to screen are more likely to have better performance because they are more actively engaging in the CRC screening process (Weiss et al., 2017). Barriers that were identified by PCPs included dealing with patients' fear of discovering cancer, belief that the screening was not effective, embarrassment and anxiety about screening, concerns about tolerating bowel preps, fear of an invasive test, and lack of awareness of screening (Sahin, Aker, & Arslan, 2017; Weiss et al., 2017). Other barriers also included PCPs who do not actively recommend CRC screening to their patients, an inadequate time during visits to discuss screening, and lack of method to identify patients in need of screening (Weiss et al., 2017).

Lafata, Cooper, Divine, Oja-Tebbe, and Flocke (2014) proposed the effectiveness of the 5As steps to discuss CRC screening with patients. The five steps include assess, advise, agree, assist, and arrange. This method is associated with improved adherence to CRC screening. The study showed that patients who received the screening recommendations through the use of the 5As steps have a higher likelihood to engage in CRC screenings in comparison to those whose visit contained no 5As (Lafata et al., 2014). The five steps method has been used in a variety of intervening communications between providers and patients, such as smoking cessation and promotion of physical activities (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, 2012; Carroll, Fiscella, Epstein, Sanders, & Williams, 2012). Therefore, this method was modified for use at the clinic during providers' communication with patients for this project.

Barriers to CRC Screening by Patients

There are many available effective CRC screening tests, but they are underused (Quick, Hester, Young, & Greiner, 2013). To improve CRC screening rates within the practice, clinicians should identify the problems causing failure to screen. Factors that may be linked to poor adherence to CRC screening include: age, sex, education level, race/ethnicity, income, marital status, fatalistic beliefs regarding cancer, and knowledge and fear of screening tests (Quick et al., 2013). Furthermore, common barriers for CRC screening that have been identified included a lack of time, patient hesitancy, and issues associated with scheduling for colonoscopy (Triantafillidis, Vagianos, Gikas, Korontzi, & Papalois, 2016; Quick et al., 2013). In addition, the lack of patient awareness and clinician recommendations should also be considered as hindrances for CRC screening (Nagelhout, Comarell, Samadder, & Wu, 2017; Triantafillidis et al., 2016).

One study proposed that CRC screening levels are suboptimal in minorities, such as Hispanic and Pacific Islanders, due to lack of trust in providers, unawareness of CRC screening, and lack of providers' communication (Nagelhout et al., 2017). For instance, Hispanic patients were less likely to report having had a clinician discuss CRC screening options with them in comparison to white patients (OR = 0.24, 95% CI: 0.09-0.68, $p < 0.05$) (Nagelhout et al., 2017). The clinicians should recognize that different cultures or races/ethnicities may have distinctive barriers; therefore, culturally tailored interventions will be crucial to improve CRC screening (Nagelhout et al., 2017; Triantafillidis et al., 2016).

Limited health literacy or limited English proficiency (LEP) are other barriers to CRC screening in certain populations (Kobayashi, Wardle, & Von Wagner, 2014; Nagelhout et al., 2017). A longitudinal study was conducted using data from the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA) to determine the association of health literacy and CRC screening. The result revealed that having adequate health literacy was associated with higher probabilities of participating in CRC screening programs than individuals with limited health literacy (Kobayashi et al., 2014). Much of the existing CRC screening information is in English; therefore, patients with LEP might have difficulty understanding the information, which could lead to lower CRC screening participation (Nagelhout et al., 2017).

Intervention to Improve CRC Screening

Reviewing barriers and factors associated with CRC screening adherence, the clinicians will be able to focus their interventions to improve CRC screening according to problems identified. A self-reported study on barriers, in racially diverse low-income

population, for FIT and colonoscopy completion suggested specific barriers for colonoscopy were due to reluctance to test (39.2%), scheduling problems (34%), lack of transportation (11.3%), health reasons (9.3%), and lack of time (8.2%). Specific FIT barriers were due to loss of the kits (20%), forgetting to complete the test, and changing decisions to do tests (35%). The study also mentioned that some patients falsely reported completion of FIT test or did not perform the test correctly (Quick et al., 2013). These issues are examples of common barriers that cause CRC screening rates to be low.

Multiple evidence-based interventions were reviewed in the literature.

Interventions encouraging patient reminders are one of the effective methods (James, Richardson, Wang, Proctor, & Colditz, 2013; Singal et al., 2016). Singal et al. (2016) conducted a double-blinded RCT to test effectiveness of FIT and colonoscopy outreach. Participants were receiving mail outreach invitations and two-week telephone follow-up reminders. The result revealed screening participation rates were higher for FIT outreach (58.8%) and colonoscopy outreach (42.4%) than usual care (29.6%) ($P < 0.001$ for both). Though the majority of patients were able to receive text messages, the text-reminder for CRC screening did not significantly improve the screening compliance (Hirst, et al., 2016).

Education is another intervention that has proven to be one effective strategy (Carney et al., 2014; Menon et al., 2011). Limited health literacy and LEP were mentioned as barriers for CRC screening (Kobayashi et al., 2014; Nagelhout et al., 2017). Therefore, tailored educational programs or information on CRC screening could help improve patient participation (Carney et al., 2014). Another RCT compared the effectiveness between telephone-based tailored education (TE), motivational interview

(MI), and usual care (UC) on CRC screening adherence. The result suggested both TE and MI groups have higher CRC screening rates compared to UC. TE has the highest screening rate (23.8 %, $p < 0.02$) and patients were 2.2 times more likely to complete the CRC screening (Menon et al., 2011). Based on the findings of this ROL, this project emphasized CRC screening for patient's age between 50 to 75 years, telephone outreach reminders, mailed FIT outreach, and educational activities to help improve screening rates within the clinic.

The Medicare Star-Rating and Provider Incentives Program

Though the CRC mortality and incidence decreased by 30% in the last 15 years, CRC is still considered as a major public health problem. Approximately, 277,000 cases and 203,000 deaths will be prevented by 2030, if the United States reaches the CRC screening goal of 80% of adults aged 50 or older by 2018 (National Colorectal Cancer Roundtable, 2019). The U.S. Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services (CMS) is one of the organizations that adapted the initiative by incorporating it into their quality measure program called the Medicare Star-Rating Program (MSRP). This program reflects Medicare Advantage plan quality. In 2011, a combination of Parts C and D overall rating was created for Medicare Advantage and Prescription Drug (MAPD) plans. The star ratings integrate data from Healthcare Effectiveness Data and Information Set quality measures, Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems surveys, the Health of Seniors survey, and other administrative data (Coronado et al., 2015; Reid, Deb, Howell, & Shrank, 2013).

In 2011, MAPD star ratings ranged from two to five stars. In 2012, the Affordable Care Act (ACA) provisions and a CMS demonstration program began to

reward plans rated three stars or more with incentives. In addition, the CMS allows five-star plans to have a year-long open enrollment. This is used to motivate insurers to improve their performance on the quality measures including CRC screening rates (Coronado et al., 2015). Though the MSRP is quite important to the insurers, it is doubtful whether the programs matter to beneficiaries (Reid et al., 2013). However, many studies still suggest that patients deliberate on quality information when it comes to choosing their health plans (Kolstad, & Chernew, 2009; Reid et al., 2013).

METHODS

The ultimate goal for this project was to improve CRC screening scores in the clinic by integrating the HBM and the TTP. The following section described the setting, parameters of the sample population, procedures, and evaluation plans.

Setting

This QI project took place in a primary care clinic in Los Angeles County. It had one large waiting room and four examination rooms. The clinic operated with two nurse practitioners, one medical doctor, and three medical assistants (MAs).

Sample

The sample population included patients aged 50 to 75 years, all genders, who presented to the clinic and were eligible for CRC screening. Eligibility was further defined for patients who had a previous recommendation for repeat screening or patients who had never had a previous CRC screening. Exclusion criteria, as shown in Table 2, were patients previously diagnosed with CRC, hospice patients, and patients that died during the data collection period.

Table 2

Exclusion Diagnoses and ICD-10 Codes

Diagnosis	ICD-10 Code
Malignant neoplasm of ascending colon	C18.2
Malignant neoplasm of transverse colon	C18.4
Malignant neoplasm of descending colon	C18.6
Malignant neoplasm of sigmoid colon	C18.7
Malignant neoplasm of colon, unspecified	C18.9
Malignant neoplasm of rectum	C20

Measures

The effectiveness of the practice changes was measured by comparing the scores provided by two medical groups responsible for resource management, hereafter referred to as Medical Group A (MGA) and Medical Group B (MGB). The scores of the last quarter reports before starting the project and the following quarter after starting the project were the basis of comparison. Chart reviews of those patients who were seen during September 25, 2018 through December 28, 2018 were for CRC screening documentation and completion. The goals of these chart reviews were to assess the associations between the two medical groups screening scores and the number of patients who received the screening at the clinic. In addition, a pre-education and post-education evaluation for providers and staff were evaluated through content analysis.

Procedures

Once the Institutional Review Board (IRB) acknowledgement was received (Appendix A), the project was discussed with the physician-owner of the clinic. The project implementation began after the owner's approval (Appendix B). For this project, the author was referred to as a "trainer." The trainer performed the following activities:

- Provided educational sessions to providers and staff, which included the importance of CRC screening, CRC screening options, and how the clinic was doing
- Administered a pre and post knowledge quiz to providers and staff on CRC
- Provided educational materials (brochures and posters) to patients (see Appendix C)

The first educational session contained evidence-based CRC screening information, CRC screening rates within the practice, implementation of the TM to help with coaching patients, and information on CRC poster and brochure. The knowledge quizzes were given to health coaches to ensure that they understood the educational materials and were ready to coach the patients. The HBM was applied to staff and providers during this session. Furthermore, the clinic performance as compared to the national benchmarks was reviewed during the session and the 5As steps implementation for the providers was included. These steps were techniques that helped providers to explain and discuss CRC screening with patients (Lafata et al., 2014). Each session took 30-45 minutes and took place during staff lunch breaks. Lunch was provided for staff and providers on the day of educational sessions. The pre and post-quizzes were given to providers and staff by the trainer on the same day. The second educational session included discussion on the progress, questions, and comments from providers and staff regarding the effectiveness of the TTP and any issues that occurred during the implementation period. Other educational activities involved brochures and posters in the patient care areas.

The TTP was modified to fit the patient flow within the clinic. For the purpose of this DNP project, the MAs were considered as health coaches after they were trained and followed these procedures:

- Verified CRC screening eligibility for patients aged 50 to 75
- Documented if the patient had been screened for CRC
- Informed the patient that providers would review CRC screening with them
- Helped answer simple questions regarding CRC screening

The next step for coaching patients was during the visit with providers. Providers performed the following activities:

- Explained importance of CRC screening, and offered the screening to the patients again
- Applied the 5A (Assess, Advise, Agree, Assist, and Arrange) steps of discussion with patients (Lafata et al., 2014). These steps included:
 - ❖ Assess patients for CRC screening eligibility
 - ❖ Provide and reinforce CRC education
 - ❖ Discuss screening options
 - ❖ Make agreement with patients
 - ❖ Arrange for the screening processes (i.e. getting authorizations, giving referrals, teaching patients how to perform stool test, and mailing the FIT test to the patient)

The third part of the TTP coaching was to check whether screening was offered to the patient. All patients who were seen by providers would have CRC screening orders. This could be either stool tests or colonoscopies. At the end of the visit, the MAs provided options to patients: either a pre-paid postcard or email address to document when the patients either made the appointment for gastroenterologist or when they sent the FIT or gFOBT to the lab. Within two weeks, the MAs checked results on electronic medical records, their emails, or postcards to see whether patients had completed the screening as recommended. Then, the MAs documented who did not complete their screening requirement as ordered. At that point, the provider decided if the patient should

be seen again or directed further MA interactions and schedule for follow up visits (Figure 2).

Figure 2. HBM and Teamlet Training Pathway (TTP).

Timeline

After IRB acknowledgement was received, the implementation of this QI project began. The project timeline is as shown in Table 3. The project proposal was presented on May 24, 2018. The pre-intervention data were requested from the two medical groups, A and B. All educational materials were retrieved by June 15, 2018. The first educational session was conducted with the physician-owner followed by a meeting with all of the providers and staff on June 21, 2018. The second educational session and meeting was conducted on October 15, 2018. This second meeting with staff was to discuss issues the staff and providers had regarding the project implementation, and to answer questions. The intervention began on September 25, 2018. The post-intervention data collection was

between December 31, 2018 and January 7, 2019. All data collection periods were consistent with the timing of metrics from the medical groups.

Table 3

Project Timeline

Date	Objectives
May 24, 2018	Project proposal presented to chair committees
June 01, 2018	Retrospective data collection of CRC screen rates
June 15, 2018	Educational PowerPoint presentation, brochures, and posters complete
September, 2018	IRB acknowledgement letter obtained
September 20, 2018	1 st Educational session with providers and staff at the clinic
September 24, 2018	Began intervention
October 15, 2018	2 nd Educational and meeting session with providers and staff at the clinic
December 30, 2018	Post-intervention data collection
February 14, 2019	Analysis of data & evaluation, then the project finalized and submitted to project chair committees

Ethical Issues

An ethical concern for this project was the need to access EMR for patient data. During chart reviews, Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act precautions applied when reviewing patient diagnosis, past medical history, and CRC screening history. Therefore, an IRB application was submitted to the California State University of Long Beach IRB and the project IRB acknowledgement (number 1259744-2) (Appendix A) was received on September 4, 2018. In addition, an approval letter from the physician-owner (Appendix B) was obtained prior to start the project.

RESULTS

The project was implemented from September 25, 2018 through December 28, 2018. Prior to the project implementation, the first educational session was given to the clinic staff and providers along with the knowledge quiz on CRC (see Appendix D). There were four MAs and the clinic physician owner attending the first educational session. The most missed question was question 6, which states “True or False, a colonoscopy is the only test available for CRC screening?” More than half of the staff responded “True.” Hence, the result revealed the area where the staff needed more education; the additional education reinforced to the staff other CRC screening tests, including stool tests (FIT or gFOBT) and colonoscopies. After the educational session was given to staff, more than 80% of staff were able to answer all of the questions on the post-test correctly.

A total of 692 patients were seen during the implementation and 370 (53.4%) patients were aged between 50 – 75 years. Chart reviews were completed to assess types of coverage and CRC screening documentation. The review of medical group coverage showed the number of patients who were covered under MGA, MGB, and other plans or self-pay. The undocumented charts were excluded from the data analysis. As demonstrated in Figure 3, 190 out of 370 patients were documented to have CRC screening, which was about 51.3%. The breakdown of payor coverage was as follows: 38 (20%) patients under MGA coverage, 48 (25.6%) under MGB coverage, and 104 (54.7%) under other coverage or self-pay. About 70% (133 of 190) documented charts revealed those patients either completed or were in a process of CRC screenings. Only 57 (30%) patients were documented to have received CRC screening orders during the time of

implementation. 30% is considerably low when comparing to the Star measure goal of 80%. This number could reflect the clinic performance on overall CRC screening.

Figure 3. Patients who were seen during the time of implementation with review of CRC screening documentation and different payor coverages.

The sample descriptive data collected from 57 patients who received CRC screening orders during the period of implementation included age, gender, and race/ethnicity. The average age of the patients was 61 years. Twenty-nine patients were males and 28 were females. There was an ideal distribution between both sexes who received the screening orders. The race/ethnicity of the sample (see Figure 4), revealed 18 (33%) Asian/Filipino, 12 (21%) Caucasian, 26 (43.8%) Hispanic, 1(0.2 %) other/unknown. None of these patients considered themselves as African American. From

this descriptive result, the clinic serves mostly Asian/Filipino and Hispanic patients, but the population that has higher risk for CRC, such as African Americans, were not included in the project implementation (Bromley, May, Federer, Spiegel, & Van Oijen, 2015; Carethers, 2014; USPSTF, 2016). Therefore, the findings from this project might not be generalizable.

Figure 4. Race/ethnicity of patients who received CRC screening orders during the project implementation.

In Table 4, the data collection was divided into three time periods. From September 25, 2018 through October 24, 2018, only seven patients received CRC screening orders. During that time, the clinic lost two of the main MAs who were trained to be health coaches for the project. The second educational session and meeting with providers and staff was completed on October 15, 2018. The discussion during this meeting involved how the overall clinic was performing with the project and questions or issues from staff and providers. The findings disclosed many limitations on the project. The staff reported the main provider was on vacation, and this led to shorter clinic time

and more scheduled patients per day. The NP reported that she was unable to fully perform the 5As steps as instructed and did not have enough time to discuss CRC screening options with patients.

Furthermore, there was only one regular MA who had to work at the desk and in-patient care areas. The staff workload affected the project process because the MA was not able to follow up with patients who did not complete CRC screening in the two-week time period. Not all of patients who needed reminder calls received them on time. Many patients came back to the office and submitted the stool testing kits. Some patients called back regarding their appointments with gastroenterologists and there were patients who had stool testing completed at the lab.

The solution was established to help providers and MAs save time during each patient visit and encourage further CRC screening. The solution was to place the FIT or gFOBT kit in front of eligible patient charts along with CRC brochures before patients were seen by providers. From the period of October 25, 2018 through November 24, 2018, the number of patients receiving stool testing kits for CRC screening was significantly increased from four to 37 patients. Instead, the number of colonoscopies declined due to the limited time with providers to discuss this option with patients. Overall, the total of patients who received orders for CRC was increased more than five times from period 1 to period 3. At the end of implementation, there were three patients who have positive stool tests and required further diagnostic tests.

Table 4

Numbers of Patients who Received CRC Screening During Data Collection

Date	Number of Patients	Colonoscopy	FIT/gFOBT
9/25/18-10/24/18 (Period 1)	7	6	1
10/25/18-11/24/18 (Period 2)	11	7	4
11/25/18-12/28/18 (Period 3)	39	2	37
Total	57	15	42

Note. A total of 57 Patients who were identified as documented to receive CRC screening orders during implementation periods.

The results from the two medical group payors, A and B (see Figures 5 and 6), revealed overall improvement of CRC screening rates. Figure 5 demonstrates MGA's CRC screening rates starting from March 2018 until December 2018. In March, the CRC screening rates on patients with Medicare was at 61.5% and commercial patient rate was 22.2% with a goal of 80%. In mid-April, the MGA screening rates went down because there were fewer providers working at the clinic during that time until the end of May. It can be seen clearly when the project leader greatly reduced her hours by the dip in April 2018's CRC screening rates. The CRC screening rate was gradually improving until mid-September. The project was initially implemented on September 25, 2018. There was no progress during the implementation, as shown in Figure 5, the AC screening rates plateaued at 56.3% and 18.8%. Overall, MGA screening rates improved by 11.9% and 4.5%, respectively. According to Figure 3, approximately 20% of documented patients that were seen had MGA coverage.

In Figure 6, the MGB results revealed 47% and 39% CRC completion in July 2018. There was a trend of gradual increases in MGB CRC screening rates. The clinic did very well with this group of patients. By the end of the December 2018, the overall rates went up to 11% Medicare patients and 12% for commercial patients respectively. About half of the patients that were seen from September 25 to December 28, 2018 were covered under MGA and MGB. Consequently, the CRC screening rates from these two medical groups provide an indication of how the clinic was performing overall with this cancer screening.

Figure 5. Medical Group A results on CRC screening from March through December 2018.

Figure 6. Medical Group B results on CRC screening from July 2018 to January 2019.

DISCUSSION

Despite the establishment of the MSRP to encourage providers to be more active with CRC screening, many providers either failed to initiate or unsuccessfully incorporate this screening into their routine practices and were unable to meet the screening goals. Upon completing this QI project, the challenges that providers encountered were shortness of staff, large workload, and limited visit time with patients; these were consistent with the review of literature (Weiss et al., 2017). The HBM and TTP facilitated the staff and providers by helping them appreciate the importance for the CRC screening and increase engaging time with patients. In addition, the TTP had allowed staff to be proactive in CRC screening, especially with stool testing (FIT or gFOBT). The pathway seems to be effective despite many limitations that occurred during the time of implementation. Though the project did not reach the national CRC screening goal of 80%, the overall CRC screening rates of both medical groups were gradually improving, especially MGB. The final data collection indicated improvement by more than 10%.

The clinic is located in Los Angeles County and serves a large population of Asian/Filipinos and Hispanics. Understanding the population that the clinic is serving can help identify present barriers. According to the literature, minorities have lower CRC screening adherence than others due to lack of trust in providers, lack of communication, and not being aware of the available screening tests (Nagelhout et al., 2017). For most of these patients English is their second language and many of them may have difficulty understanding the instructions that they were given in regard to the screening. Addressing these population-based barriers could increase the CRC screening completion within the clinic.

Limitations

Implementation of this project was amended because of staff shortage. An alternative plan was developed to support the providers and MAs to be able to continue promoting CRC screening within the clinic. During the data collection time from September to December, many coverage claims had not yet reached the medical groups for reimbursement, particularly colonoscopies which take a longer time to process.

Recommendation for Practice

The application of the TTP illustrates that good teamwork and support from team members can facilitate the team to meet their goals. A similar project could be implemented in other primary care settings and benefit an organization by identifying the same issues found at this clinic. A longer data collection time could produce more accurate CRC screening rates and available results. Because the setting of the project was a small private clinic, implementing the TTP in larger organizations may also demonstrate different results.

The lack of success in meeting higher scores in this clinic informed the author that more time and energy is needed for organizational change. After completing this project, the clinic had demonstrated awareness of their barriers and a willingness to change. Encouraging CRC screening can be challenging. If providers take the time to explain the importance of the screenings and the consequences of not completing them, patients might be more willing to complete these tests. Lastly, understanding the barriers of CRC screening in different populations and modifying the strategies to tailor-fit those populations may also help promote the screenings as well.

REFERENCES

- Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality. (2012). Five major steps to intervention (The “5 A’s”). Retrieved from <https://www.ahrq.gov/professionals/clinicians-providers/guidelines-recommendations/tobacco/5steps.html>
- American Cancer Society. (2019). Colorectal facts & figures 2017-2019. Retrieved from <https://www.cancer.org/content/dam/cancer-org/research/cancer-facts-and-statistics/colorectal-cancer-facts-and-figures/colorectal-cancer-facts-and-figures-2017-2019.pdf>
- American Cancer Society. (2018). Key statistics for colon cancer. Retrieved from <https://www.cancer.org/cancer/colon-rectal-cancer/about/key-statistics.html>
- American Cancer Society. (2018). What are survival rates of colorectal cancer, by stage? Retrieved from <https://www.cancer.org/cancer/colon-rectal-cancer/detection-diagnosis-staging/survival-rates.html>
- American Cancer Society. (2018). What is colorectal cancer? Retrieved from <https://www.cancer.org/cancer/colon-rectal-cancer/about/what-is-colorectal-cancer.html>
- American Psychological Association. (2018). Teaching tip sheet: self-efficacy. Retrieved from <http://www.apa.org/pi/aids/resources/education/self-efficacy.aspx>
- Bodenheimer, T., & Laing, B. (2007). The teamlet model of primary care. *Annals of Family Medicine, 5*(5), 457-61.
- Bromley, May, Federer, Spiegel, & Van Oijen. (2015). Explaining persistent under-use of colonoscopic cancer screening in African Americans: A systematic review. *Preventive Medicine, 71*, 40-48.

- Carethers, J. (2015). Screening for colorectal cancer in African Americans: Determinants and rationale for an earlier age to commence screening. *Digestive Diseases and Sciences*, *60*(3), 711-721.
- Carney, P. A., Lee-Lin, F., Mongoue-Tchokote, S., Mori, M., Leung, H., Lau, C., & Lieberman, D. (2014). Improving colorectal cancer screening in Asian Americans: Results of a randomized intervention study. *Cancer*, *120*(11), 1702-1712.
- Carpenter, C. J. (2010). A meta-analysis of the effectiveness of health belief model variables in predicting behavior. *Health Communication*, *25*(8), 661-669.
doi:10.1080/10410236.2010.521906
- Carroll, J., Fiscella, K., Epstein, R., Sanders, M., & Williams, G. (2012). A 5A's communication intervention to promote physical activity in underserved populations. *BMC Health Services Research*, *12*, 374.
- Causey, C., & Greenwald, B. (2011). Promoting community awareness of the need for colorectal cancer prevention and screening: A Replication Study. *Gastroenterology Nursing*, *34*(1), 34-40
- Center of Disease Control and Prevention. (2017). Chronic disease overview. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/chronicdisease/overview/index.htm>
- Center of Disease Control and Prevention. (2017). Colorectal cancer statistics. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/colorectal/statistics/index.htm>
- Center of Disease Control and Prevention. (2018). Use of colorectal cancer screening tests by states. Retrieved from

<https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/dcpc/research/articles/use-colorectal-screening-tests-state.htm>

- Chubak, J., Bogart, A., Fuller, S., Laing, S. S., & Green B. B. (2013). Uptake and positive predictive value of fecal occult blood tests: A randomized controlled trial. *Preventive Medicine, 57*, 671-678. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ypmed.2013.08.032>
- Clinical Correlation. (2015). There's an app for that: fitness apps and behavior change theory. Retrieved from <https://www.clinicalcorrelations.org/?p=8693>
- Coronado, G. D., Petrik, A. F., Bartelmann, S. E., Coyner, L. A., & Coury, J. (2015). Health policy to promote colorectal cancer screening: Improving access and aligning federal and state incentives. *Clinical Researcher (Alexandria, Va.)*, 29(1), 50–55. <http://doi.org/10.14524/CR-14-0044>
- Genetech. (2012). What is colorectal cancer? Retrieved from <https://www.gene.com/stories/understanding-colorectal-cancer>
- Grunfeld, E., Manca, D., Moineddin, R., Thorpe, K. E., Hoch, J. S., Campbell-Scherer, D., Mamdani, M. (2013). Improving chronic disease prevention and screening in primary care: results of the better pragmatic cluster randomized controlled trial. *BMC Family Practice, 14*, 175. <http://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2296-14-175>
- Gupta, Brenner, Ratanawongsa, & Inadomi. (2014). Patient trust in physician influences colorectal cancer screening in low-income patients. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine, 47*(4), 417-423.
- James, A., Richardson, V., Wang, J., Proctor, E., & Colditz, G. (2013). Systems intervention to promote colon cancer screening in safety net settings: Protocol for

a community-based participatory randomized controlled trial. *Implementation Science* 8, (58).

Johns Hopkins University. (2016). Urban adolescent SRH SBCC implementation kit.

Retrieved from <https://sbccimplementationkits.org/urban-youth/health-belief-model/>

Hack, F., Hall, M., Hummer, M., & Pruckner, G.J. (2015). The effectiveness of health screening. *Health Economics*, 24(8), 913-935. doi: 10.1002/hec.3072

Hirst, Y., Skrobanski, H., Kerrison, R.S., Kobayashi, L.C., Counsell, N., Djedovic, N., Ruwende, J., Von Wagner, C. (2016). Text-message reminders in colorectal cancer screening: A non-clinical randomized controlled trial. *The Lancet*, 388, S55.

Holme, Ø., Løberg, M., Kalager, M., Bretthauer, M., Hernán, M. A., Aas, E., & Hoff, G. (2014). Effect of flexible sigmoidoscopy screening on colorectal cancer incidence and mortality: A randomized clinical trial. *Journal of American Medical Association*, 312(6), 606-615. doi:10.1001/jama.2014.8266

Honein-Abouhaidar, G., Kastner, M., Vuong, V., Perrier, L., Rabeneck, L., Tinmouth, J., Baxter, N. (2014). Benefits and barriers to participation in colorectal cancer screening: A protocol for a systematic review and synthesis of qualitative studies. *BMJ Open*, 4(2).

Kobayashi, Wardle, & Von Wagner. (2014). Limited health literacy is a barrier to colorectal cancer screening in England: Evidence from the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing. *Preventive Medicine*, 61, 100-105.

- Kolstad, J., & Chernew, M. (2009). Quality and consumer decision making in the market for health insurance and health care services. *Medical Care Research and Review*, 66(1_suppl), 28S-52S.
- Lafata, J.E., Cooper, G., Divine, G., Oja-Tebbe, N., & Flocke, S.A. (2014). Patient-physician colorectal cancer screening discussion content and patients' use of colorectal cancer screening. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 94(1), 76-82.
- Lin, J. S, Piper, M. A., Perdue, L. A., Rutter, C. M., Webber, E. M., O'Connor, E., & Whitlock, E. P. (2016). Screening for colorectal cancer: Updated evidence report and systematic review for the United States Preventive Services Task Force. *Journal of American Medical Association*, 315(23), 2576-2594. doi: 10.1001/jama.2016.3332
- Manser, C.N., Bachmann, L.M., Brunner, J., Hunold, F., Bauerfeind, P., & Marbet, U.A. (2012). Colonoscopy screening markedly reduces the occurrence of colon carcinomas and carcinoma-related death: A closed cohort study. *Gastroenterology*, 142(5), S573.
- Meester, R., Doubeni, C., Zauber, A., Goede, S., Levin, T., Corley, D., Lansdorp-Vogelaar, I. (2015). Public health impact of achieving 80% colorectal cancer screening rates in the United States by 2018. *Cancer*, 121(13), 2281-2285.
- Menon, U., Belue, R., Wahab, S., Rugen, K., Kinney, A., Maramaldi, Y., Szalacha, D. (2011). A randomized trial comparing the effect of two phone-based interventions on colorectal cancer screening adherence. *Annals of Behavioral Medicine*, 42(3), 294-303.

- Miller, W. & Rollnick, S. (2013). Colorectal screening discussion scripts for healthcare providers using motivational interviewing communication techniques. Retrieved from https://www.ndcancercoalition.org/image/cache/Provider_Discussion_Script_for_Colorectal_Cancer_Screening.pdf
- Mosen, D. M., Feldstein, A. C., Perrin, N., Rosales, A. G., Smith, D. H., Liles, E. G., Elston-Lafata, J. (2013). More comprehensive discussion of CRC screening associated with higher screening. *The American Journal of Managed Care*, 19(4), 265–271.
- National Colorectal Cancer Roundtable. (2019). Data & progress. Retrieved from <http://nccrt.org/data-progress/>
- National Colorectal Cancer Roundtable. (2018). Working toward the shared goal of 80% screened for colorectal cancer by 2018. Retrieved from <http://nccrt.org/what-we-do/80-percent-by-2018/>
- Nagelhout, E., Comarell, K., Samadder, N., & Wu, J. (2017). Barriers to colorectal cancer screening in a racially diverse population served by a safety-net clinic. *Journal of Community Health*, 42(4), 791-796.
- Ngo, V., Hammer, H., & Bodenheimer, T. (2010). Health coaching in the Teamlet Model: A Case Study. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 25(12), 1375-1378.
- Peterson, E.B., Ostroff, J.S., Duhamel, K. N., D’Agostino, T.A., Hernandez, M., Canzona, M. R., & Bylund, C.L. (2016). Impact of provider-patient communication on cancer screening adherence: A systematic review. *Preventive Medicine*, 93, 96-105.

- Quick, B.W., Hester, C.M., Young, K.L., & Greiner, K.A. (2013). Self-reported barriers to colorectal cancer screening in a racially diverse, low-income study population. *Journal of Community Health, 38*(2), 285-292.
- Reid, R., Deb, P., Howell, B., & Shrank, W. (2013). Association between Medicare Advantage Plan Star Ratings and Enrollment. *JAMA, 309*(3), 267-274.
- Rosenstock, I. (2005). Why people use health services. *Milbank Quarterly, 83*(4), 1-32.
- Sahin, M., Aker, K., & Arslan, S. (2017). Barriers to colorectal cancer screening in a primary care setting in Turkey. *Journal of Community Health, 42*(1), 101-108
- Singal, A., Gupta, S., Tiro, J., Skinner, C., McCallister, K., Sanders, J., & Halm, E. (2016). Outreach invitations for FIT and colonoscopy improve colorectal cancer screening rates: A randomized controlled trial in a safety-net health system. *Cancer, 122*(3), 456-463.
- Smith, R., Andrews, K., Brooks, D., Fedewa, S., Manassaram-Baptiste, D., Saslow, D., Wender, R. (2017). Cancer screening in the United States, 2017: A review of current American Cancer Society guidelines and current issues in cancer screening. *CA: A Cancer Journal for Clinicians, 67*(2), 100-121.
- Smith, R., Manassaram-Baptiste, D., Brooks, D., Doroshenk, M., Fedewa, S., Saslow, D., Wender, R. (2015). Cancer screening in the united states, 2015: A review of current American Cancer Society guidelines and current issues in cancer screening. *CA: A Cancer Journal for Clinicians, 65*(1), 30-54.
- Triantafillidis, J.K., Vagianos, C., Gikas, A., Korontzi, M., & Papalois, A. (2016). Screening for colorectal cancer: The role of the primary care physician. *European Journal of Gastroenterology & Hepatology, 29*(1).

- University of Twente. (2017). Health belief model. Retrieved from https://www.utwente.nl/en/bms/communication-theories/sorted-by-cluster/Health%20Communication/Health_Belief_Model/
- U.S. Preventative Services Task Force. (2016). U.S. Preventative Services Task Force recommendation statement: Screening for colorectal cancer U.S.
- Weiss, J.M., Pickhardt, P.J., Schumacher, J.R., Potvien, A., Kim, D.H., Pfau, P.R., Smith, M.A. (2017). Primary care provider perceptions of colorectal cancer screening barriers: Implications for designing quality improvement interventions. *Gastroenterology Research and Practice*, (1), 1-10.
- Wools, A., Dapper, E., & Leeuw, J. (2016). Colorectal cancer screening participation: A systematic review. *The European Journal of Public Health*, 26(1), 158-168.

APPENDIX A

IRB ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH

OFFICE OF RESEARCH & SPONSORED PROGRAMS

DATE: September 4, 2018

TO: panujee bijayathin

FROM: CSULB IRB

PROJECT TITLE: [1259744-2] Improving colorectal cancer screening rate in a primary care setting

REFERENCE #: 18-447

SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project

REVIEW TYPE: Administrative Review

ACTION: ACKNOWLEDGED

EFFECTIVE DATE: September 4, 2018

Thank you for submitting the New Project materials for this Quality Assurance/Quality Improvement project. The California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board has ACKNOWLEDGED your submission. No further action on submission 1259744-2 is required at this time.

The following items are acknowledged in this submission:

- IRB Application Form

Your project is considered Exempt according to the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services regulation at 45 CFR 46.101(b)(2) and therefore will not expire under the condition that the project continues to abide by University Policy regarding with Human subjects:

1. If you need to make changes/revisions to this approved project, you must submit a Request for Amendment to an Approved Protocol in addition to any documents affected by the requested change. Submit these documents as a subsequent package to your approved project via IRBNet. The CSULB IRB must approve the requested changes prior to implementing the changes to your project.
2. You are required to inform the Director of Research Integrity and Compliance, Office of Research & Sponsored Programs, via email ORSPCompliance@csulb.edu within twenty-four hours of any adverse event in the conduct of research involving human subjects. The report shall include the nature of the adverse event, the names of the persons affected, the extent of the injury or breach of security, if any, and any other information material to the situation.
3. Maintain your research records as detailed in the protocol.
4. Respond to the Annual Check-In notice via IRBNet if you intend to continue the project after September 3, 2019

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH

SCHOOL OF NURSING

Faculty Advisor Statement

TO: CSULB Institutional Review Board

FROM: Panujee Bijayayothin, MSN, RN, FNP-C

NAME OF STUDENT: Panujee Bijayayothin, MSN, RN, FNP-C

TITLE OF PROJECT: Improving Colorectal Cancer Screening in Primary Care

STATEMENT OF THE ADVISOR:

I, Annie Odell, PhD, FNP, certify that I have reviewed and confirmed the following regarding the aforementioned project:

- The student and I have discussed and reviewed the submission for appropriateness and completeness with regard to the collection and protection of subject data.
- The research methodologies align with acceptable methodologies of this discipline.
- The risk/benefit ratio is appropriate for the project activities.
- The potential risks include: None to low-potential risk of loss of confidentiality
- The appropriate safeguards in place to minimize the risks include: 1) Students are required to complete the CITI training by the CSULB policy to familiarize themselves with the regulations and understand the risks involved in the projects they are conducting for their doctoral projects. 2) Data that is collected will be deidentified as soon as necessary data collection is completed. 3) All personal identifying data that will be collected will be separated from the data needed for the project and will be saved in a locked location and on encrypted computers protected by user password and only accessed by the students conducting the project. The personal identifying data will be destroyed as soon as sufficient data has been collected.
- I will continue supervision of this project and ensure the student remains compliant with CSULB research policies by having frequent communication with Panujee Bijayayothin, overseeing her progress and data collection methods.

My signature below certifies that I as the Faculty Advisor of this research have read and approved the attached IRB Application.

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH

SCHOOL OF NURSING

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be "Annie Odell", written over a horizontal line. The signature is stylized and includes a large "X" at the beginning.

Faculty Advisor/Thesis Chair

[CSULB School of Nursing]
Phone: 626-841-8328
[Annie.odell@csulb.edu]

APPENDIX B
PHYSICIAN-OWNER APPROVAL

June 4, 2018

Panujee Bijayayothin, MSN, RN, FNP-C

Dear Panujee Bijayayothin, MSN, RN, FNP-C

I approve of you, Panujee Bijayayothin, MSN, RN, FNP-C to collect data for your doctoral project from employees and patients within the Core Healthcare Group Clinic. Employees may participate in your study titled "Improving Colorectal Screening Rate in Primary Care."

You will be provided with the work email addresses of employees eligible for your study and will be allowed to directly email your survey invitations to them.

Additionally, I understand that I will only be receiving the final draft of the project paper and not have any additional data and analyses.

Sincerely,

Dr. Francisco Badar, MD

Owner/ Physician of Core Healthcare Group
City of Cerritos, California

APPENDIX C

CRC MATERIALS FOR PATIENTS

WHAT IS COLORECTAL CANCER?

Colorectal cancer, or CRC, is the third most commonly diagnosed cancer in both men and women in the United States, and the second leading overall cause of cancer deaths.¹

WHO GETS CRC?

More than **90%** of CRCs occur in people age **50 and older²**

CRC incidence is:

35%-40% more common in men than women²

20% higher among African Americans than whites²

HOW DOES CRC DEVELOP?

- 1 Most CRC begins as a non-cancerous growth called a polyp that forms on the innermost layer of the colon or rectum. Some polyps can become cancerous¹
- 2 As a CRC tumor develops, it grows through several layers of tissue¹
- 3 Eventually the tumor may reach nearby lymph and blood vessels, and may even spread to lymph nodes and distant sites in the body¹

HOW MANY ARE AFFECTED?

More than **140,000** Americans are diagnosed each year¹ that's about **16** every hour¹

Each Year **28,700** people are diagnosed with metastatic CRC, or advanced stage disease²

50,000 Americans will die from the disease each year¹

CRC incidence has been increasing in adults **<50²**

CATCHING CRC EARLY IS IMPORTANT

more than **9 out of 10** individuals diagnosed with early stage CRC that has not spread (metastasized) beyond the colon or rectum

SURVIVE 5 YEARS⁴
(and many live much longer)

approximately **1 out of 10** individuals with advanced stage CRC that has spread (metastasized) to other organs such as the lungs or the liver

SURVIVES 5 YEARS⁴

Because the early stages of the disease do not typically cause symptoms, the American Cancer Society recommends **screening tests beginning at age 50** for those at average risk for CRC²

WHAT ARE SOME WARNING SIGNS?

- Changes in bowel habits, such as diarrhea, constipation or narrowing of the stool²
- A constant need to evacuate the bowel²
- Blood in the stool²
- Weakness & fatigue²
- Cramping or abdominal pain²
- Unintended weight loss²

References:

1. American Cancer Society, Colorectal Cancer Detailed Guide. <http://www.cancer.org/acs/groups/cid/documents/webcontent/003096.pdf>
2. American Cancer Society, Colorectal Cancer Facts & Figures 2011-2013. <http://www.cancer.org/acs/groups/content/@epidemiologysurveillance/documents/document/acspc-028323.pdf>
3. National Cancer Institute Surveillance Epidemiology and End Results Stat Fact Sheet: Colon and Rectum. <http://seer.cancer.gov/statfacts/html/colorect.html#survival>
4. American Cancer Society, Facts & Figures 2012. <http://www.cancer.org/acs/groups/content/@epidemiologysurveillance/documents/document/acspc-031941.pdf>

www.gene.com
Assembled by Genentech, a member of the Roche Group. ©Copyright 2012 Genentech USA, Inc. All rights reserved. Genentech
A Member of the Roche Group

Note. CRC poster posted in patient exam rooms during project implementation. Retrieved from <https://www.gene.com/stories/understanding-colorectal-cancer>

WHICH TEST IS RIGHT FOR YOU?

There is no single "best test" for any person. Each test has advantages and disadvantages. Talk to your doctor about which test or tests are right for you, and how often you should be screened.

RESOURCES
For more information:
Visit www.cdc.gov/screenforlife
Call 1-800-CDC-INFO (1-800-232-4636)
For TTY, call 1-888-232-6348

COLORECTAL CANCER SCREENING SAVES LIVES

Colorectal cancer is the second leading cancer killer—but it doesn't have to be.

BOTH MEN AND WOMEN ARE AT RISK FOR COLORECTAL CANCER.

SCREENING SAVES LIVES
Among cancers that affect both men and women, colorectal cancer is the 2nd leading cancer killer in the U.S. But it doesn't have to be. There is strong scientific evidence that screening for colorectal cancer beginning at age 50 saves lives!

WHAT IS COLORECTAL CANCER?
Cancer is a disease in which cells in the body grow out of control. Cancer is always named for the part of the body where it starts, even if it spreads to other parts of the body later. Colorectal cancer is cancer that occurs in the colon or rectum. The colon is the large intestine or large bowel. The rectum is the passageway that connects the colon to the anus.

If you're 50 or older, getting a colorectal cancer screening test could save your life.

HERE'S HOW:

- Colorectal cancer usually starts from precancerous polyps (abnormal growths) in the colon or rectum. A polyp is a growth that shouldn't be there.
- Over time, some polyps can turn into cancer.
- Screening tests can find precancerous polyps, so they can be removed before they turn into cancer.
- Screening tests can also find colorectal cancer early, when treatment works best.

U.S. Department of Health and Human Services
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention

CDC Publication #99-6948, Revised April 2017

WHO GETS COLORECTAL CANCER?

Colorectal cancer occurs most often in people aged 50 years or older. The risk increases with age. Both men and women can get colorectal cancer. If you are 50 or older, talk to your doctor about getting screened.

AM I AT INCREASED RISK?
Your risk for colorectal cancer may be higher than average if:

- You or a close relative have had colorectal polyps or colorectal cancer.
- You have inflammatory bowel disease, Crohn's disease, or ulcerative colitis.
- You have a genetic syndrome such as familial adenomatous polyposis (FAP) or hereditary non-polyposis colorectal cancer.

If you think you may be at increased risk for colorectal cancer, speak with your doctor about when to start screening, which test is right for you, and how often you should be tested.

WHAT ARE THE SYMPTOMS OF COLORECTAL CANCER?

People who have polyps or colorectal cancer don't always have symptoms, especially at first. Someone could have polyps or colorectal cancer and not know it. If there are symptoms, they may include:

- Blood in or on your stool (bowel movement).
- Pains, aches, or cramps in your stomach that don't go away.
- Losing weight and you don't know why.

If you have any of these symptoms, talk to your doctor. They may be caused by something other than cancer. However, the only way to know what is causing them is to see your doctor.

FREE OR LOW-COST SCREENING
Colorectal cancer screening tests may be covered by your health insurance policy without a deductible or co-pay. Check with your plan to find out which tests are covered for you.

Where feasible, some states in CDC's Colorectal Cancer Control Program provide free or low-cost screenings to those who are eligible. To learn more, visit www.cdc.gov/cancer/crcrccp/contact.htm or call 1-800-CDC-INFO (1-800-232-4636).

TYPES OF SCREENING TESTS

The U.S. Preventive Services Task Force recommends that adults aged 50–75 be screened for colorectal cancer. The decision to be screened after age 75 should be made on an individual basis. If you are aged 76–85, ask your doctor if you should be screened.

Several different screening tests can be used to find polyps or colorectal cancer. They include:

Flexible Sigmoidoscopy (Flex Sig)
The doctor puts a short, thin, flexible, lighted tube into your rectum, and checks for polyps or cancer inside the rectum and lower third of the colon.
How often: Every five years, or every 10 years with FIT every year.

Colonoscopy
Similar to flexible sigmoidoscopy, except the doctor uses a longer, thin, flexible, lighted tube to check for polyps or cancer inside the rectum and the entire colon. During the test, the doctor can find and remove most polyps and some cancers. Colonoscopy also is used as a follow-up test if anything unusual is found during one of the other screening tests.
How often: Every 10 years.

CT Colonography (Virtual Colonoscopy)
Computed tomography (CT) colonography, also called a virtual colonoscopy, uses X-rays and computers to produce images of the entire colon. The images are displayed on a computer screen for the doctor to analyze.
How often: Every five years.

Stool Tests
There are two types of FOBT tests. **Guaiac-based Fecal Occult Blood Test (gFOBT)** uses the chemical guaiac to detect blood in stool, while **Fecal Immunochemical Test (FIT)** uses antibodies to detect blood in the stool. You receive a test kit from your health care provider. At home, you use a stick or brush to obtain a small amount of stool. You return the test to the doctor or a lab, where stool samples are checked for blood.

The third type of stool test is the **FIT-DNA test (or Stool DNA test)** which combines the FIT with a test to detect altered DNA in stool. You collect an entire bowel movement and send it to a lab to be checked for cancer cells.
How often: gFOBT once a year. FIT once a year. FIT-DNA test once every year or three years.

COLORECTAL CANCER IS THE SECOND LEADING CANCER KILLER — BUT IT DOESN'T HAVE TO BE.

Note. CRC Brochure. Retrieved from https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/colorectal/pdf/sfl_brochure.pdf

APPENDIX D**KNOWLEDGE QUIZ FOR STAFF AND PROVIDERS**

1. *Colorectal cancer—cancer of the colon or rectum—is the third most common cancer in U.S. men and women.*

A. True B. False

2. *Colorectal cancer strikes older adults more frequently than those younger than 50.*

A. True B. False

3. *Colorectal cancer can develop with few or no symptoms.*

A. True B. False

4. *Colorectal cancer can develop anywhere in the large intestine, which includes the colon and rectum.*

A. True B. False

5. *A family history of colorectal cancer puts a person at greater risk for developing colorectal cancer.*

A. True B. False

6. *A colonoscopy is the only test available for colorectal cancer screening.*

A. True B. False

Retrieved from <https://www.urmc.rochester.edu/encyclopedia/content.aspx?contenttypeid=40&contentid=ColonQuiz>

APPENDIX E
TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Table 1

Guidelines on CRC Screening

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To evaluate the effectiveness of SIG screening on CRC incidence and mortality in a pop.-based study (Holme et al., 2014).	RCT	CG: n = 78,220	SIG & FOBT	n = 44,474(aged 50-54 years) & n = 55,736 (aged 55-64 years)	In Norway, a single SIG screening or SIG & FOBT reduced CRC incidence & mortality on a pop. level compared with no screening.
	CG: Unscreened	IG: n = 20,572	CRC mortality within 10 years of screening	63% Adherence with screening CRC	
	IG: Screened	Arm 1: 10, 283 SIG Arm 2: 10,289 SIG & FOBT		IG mortality: n = 71 CG mortality: n = 330 (31.4 vs 43.1 deaths per 100,000 persons-year, ARD 11.7 (95% CI, 3.0-20.4), HR 0.73 (95% CI, 0.56-0.94).	Mortality rates were based on public registries & didn't include a death review committees or rigorous reviewing of death certificates.
	DV: CRC incidences & related mortality	IC: aged 50-64, with no hx of CRC		IG CRC incidence: n = 253 CG CRC incidence: n = 1,086 (112.6 vs 141.0 cases per 100,000 persons-year, ARD 28.4 (95%CI, 12.1- 44.7), HR 0.8 (95% CI, 0.7-0.92).	
	Adherence with screening recommendations	Setting: Oslo city & Telemark County, Norway.		There was reduction in CRC incidences in both groups and there was no difference between solely SIG vs SIG and FOBT.	Note: The study shows the important of flexible sig. in reduction of CRC incidence & mortality

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To systematically evaluate the efficiency of CRC screening tests & harms from CRC screening, & update relevant evidence and to help inform a separate modeling exercise, since 2008 version of USPSTF CRC recommendations (Lin et al., 2016).	Design: systematic review IV: CRC screening tests DV: the effectiveness & harms of CRC screen tests	Sample: KQ1: n = 47 articles, KQ2: n = 42 articles, KQ3: n = 113 articles Setting: U.S.	Searches of Medline, PubMed & the Cochrane Central register of Controlled trials for relevant studies published from 01/08-12/31/14, with surveillance through 2/23/16 2 reviewers	Effectiveness of screening (KQ1) = SIG associated with reduced CRC-specific mortality compared with no screening, gFOBT associated with reduction in CRC for biennial screening with hemooccult II Test performance characteristics (KQ2) = CTC with bowel preparation, the per-person sensitivity to detect adenomas >10mm 67% (95% CI, 45-84%) to 94% (95% CI, 84-98%), colono. sensitivity 89% (95%CI, 78-96%) to 98% (95%CI, 74-100%). Colono. to detect adenoma >6mm ranged from 75% (95%CI, 63-84%) to 93% (95%CI, 88-96%). Harms of screening (KQ3) = 12 studies reported estimates exposure to radiation & 21 studies reported info. Findings outside colon. Endoscopy harms include risks of perforations from colonoscopy (4 in 10,000 procedures), major bleeding (8 in 10,000 procedures). FIT showed good sensitivity (73-88%), and specificity (90-96%). FIT with DNA testing had better sensitivity.	The review didn't address issues in screening high-risk adults, risk assessment for tailor screening, test acceptability, availability of or access to screening tests, methods to improve screening adherence, possible harms of over diagnosis or unnecessary polypectomy, overuse or misuse of screening, and surveillance after adenoma detection. Limited to articles that were published in English only. Note:

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To compare the incidence of CRC and CRC mortality after a single screening colono. from screened and non-screened parti. (Manser et al., 2012)	Closed cohort study	CG: n = 20,774	Colono.	The CRC incidences in the screened parti. are significantly lower in comparison to the unscreened group (adjusted OR 0.31; 95% confidence interval, 0.16-0.59; $P < 0.01$).	In general population, colono. with possible polypectomy significantly decreases CRC incidence & CRC related mortality.
	IG: screened	IG: n = 1,912			
	CG: unscreened	IC: aged 50-80			
	DV: CRC incidences & related mortality	Setting: a rural area of Switzerland where a low level of pop. migration. The areas were identified as cantons of Uri and Glarus.			
				The CRC mortality in the screened group is also lower than the unscreened group (adjusted OR 0.12; 95% 0.01-0.93; $P = 0.04$).	Homogeneity, small size of cohort, & lack of randomization.
				Both groups of parti. have similar risk factors.	Note: The study shows the important of colono. in reduction of CRC incidence & mortality.
				A positive family history of CRC and smoking were identified as significant risk factors.	
				Blue-collar workers had a higher incidence of CRC in comparison to professionals.	

Table 2

Barriers for CRC Screening by Providers

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To assess a group of PCPs based on their perceptions on CRC screening barriers and association to CRC screening rates prior to design & implement QI interv. (Weiss et al., 2017)	Retrospective cohort study IV: Barriers to CRC screening by PCPs DV: CRC screening performance	N = 166 PCPs; 39,430 pt. eligible for CRC screening IC: worked in primary care clinics that serve pt eligible for CRC screening Setting: U.S.	Surveys of CRC beliefs & practice	Response rate → 70% (n = 166/266) 2 distinctive groups: PCPs identified multiple barriers: n = 75, this group more likely to perform better & report barriers (OR, 4.14; 95% CI, 2.43–7.08) PCPs identified no major barriers: n = 91, Target high performers when conduct barriers assessment High performers were able to identify barriers in different health system levels due to more engage in CRC screening.	Findings were from large academic physician groups, which could impact generalizability. Nearly all-white pop. Potential biases on survey selections The surveys report perceptions on barriers to CRC screening were done in 2009-2010, results may not change from previous data. Note:

Table 3

Barriers for CRC Screening in Patients

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To determine the association between health literacy & participation in CRC screening in England (Kobayashi et al., 2014).	Longitudinal cohort study IV: health literacy DV: CRC screening participation rate	N = 8,741 IC: Age \geq 50 Setting: England	ELSA	Health literacy was non-differential by gender, but those with higher education more likely to have higher health literacy. Proceeded to interview: n = 3,087 The participation rate for FOBT was 55% among those with adequate health literacy, 48% for those with limited health literacy. Adequate health literacy associated with higher probability to participate in CRC screening.	The ELSA is not a good representative for the general English screening eligible pop. Only 2% of the sample were non-white. Cancer screening questions were delayed during ELSA fieldwork; therefore, parti. in our sample with no educational qualifications might not receive those questions. Note:
To identify differences in the endorsement of barriers to CRC screening & to determine the association between provider recommendation & CRC screening	Cross-sectional surveys IV: race/cultural influences; barriers to CRC screening,	N = 197 IC: aged 50-75 Setting: Salt Lake City, Utah	Self-report survey (yes/no response) on barriers to, awareness of, & occurrences of providers recommendations on CRC.	Response rate 26% → questions addressed language barriers, low health literacy. Half (50%) completed surveys in English, the remainders completed in Spanish. Screening rates = < 30% were up-to-	Questions on survey only address colono. & stool tests. Self-reported surveys, small sample size, & very low response rate (26%)

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
adherence in Hispanic, Pacific islander, & White patients (Nagelhout, 2017).	DV: adherence to CRC screening recommendation			<p>date with CRC screening</p> <p>Hispanics < Whites to report having completed a colonos. & stool tests</p> <p>Pacific Islanders < Whites to report having completed a colonos. & stool tests</p> <p>Barriers = fear for test results (28%), unable to leave work for test (27%), being unaware of the need for screening (25%), & lack of provider communication (25%)</p> <p>Hispanic reports more barriers than other groups.</p> <p>Different race/ethnicity has different common barriers.</p>	<p>Patient report for provider recommendation could be underestimate due to language barriers or other communication challenges.</p> <p>The results emphasized the need for tailored educational program/interventions in racially diverse clinics.</p> <p>Note: The study is more specific towards Hispanic patients on barriers to CRC & addressed lack of data on screening rates, barriers and provider communication in Pacific Islander patients.</p>
to analyze the effect of certain test-specific barriers have on colonos. and FIT completion in racially diverse low-income population & to determine rationales for not completing the screenings (Quick et al., 2013).	<p>Self-reported surveys</p> <p>IV: Culturally tailored education & info on CRC</p> <p>DV: adherence to FIT & colonos.</p>	<p>N = 470</p> <p>Preferred FIT: n = 167</p> <p>Preferred colonos.: n = 251</p> <p>Preferred no test: n = 52</p> <p>IC: individuals with no high-risk CRC</p>	<p>Self-reported survey (Likert scale)</p>	<p>Colonos. barriers = lack of time ($p = 0.001$), & problems getting to and from the apt ($p < 0.001$).</p> <p>FIT-specific barriers = problems keeping track of cards ($p = 0.003$), never getting around to putting stools on cards ($p = 0.006$) & forget to mail cards back ($p < 0.001$).</p>	<p>Surveys response rates were high for those who completed the screenings.</p> <p>Low response rates could affect the results if responders held different views than non-responders.</p>

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
	Barriers to complete FIT & colonos.	(ie. IBDs, history of adenomatous polyps), low- income individuals ≥ 50 years, who are not up-to-date with the USPSTF CRC recommendations Setting: Safe net Clinic in Kansas City		Rationales for non-adherence = reluctant (39.2%), scheduling problems (34%), transportation problems (11.3%), health reasons (9.3%), and being too busy (8.2%) Few reasons FIT adherence = change their mind (35%), self-reported FIT completion with no results (32%)	All screening and education were given at no cost. Note: This is the first study to show rationale on switching CRC test modalities.
To re-evaluate factors related to adherence to CRC screening programs from published literature and comparing to the pop. based -government funded programs (Wools et al., 2016).	Systematic review IV: Barriers/facilitators of CRC screening DV: adherence of CRC screening Socio-demographic Environmental Health behaviors	N = 79 IC: Age ≥ 50 , full-text in English needs to be available Setting: Netherlands	Search through EMBASE, COCHRANE, PubMed for facilitators and barriers of CRC screening	Barriers for CRC screening includes Gender male >female Age younger >older, less participate after age 80 Socio-demographic factors = less participation in minorities (Asian, Hispanic, /Latino, and other). Higher screening rate in Caucasians. The highest among African-American group. Environmental characteristic = no health insurance coverage, living in rural areas Healthcare utilization = less contact with healthcare providers less participation Health behaviors and status characteristics = former smokers	No meta-analysis due to heterogeneity of the studies. Many theoretical frameworks developed to understand CRC screening behaviors, but most often used was health behavior model. Some articles might be overlooked and many of the studies included were self-reported screening adherence. Results maybe misjudged, because some of the screening tests were not according to the current guidelines.

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
				>current smokers Negative perceptions such as pain, embarrassment and afraid are less likely to get screen.	Note:

Table 4

Interventions to Improve CRC Screening

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To test the impact of CRC screening education. by trained community health workers among Chinese, Korean, and Vietnamese parti. (Carney et al., 2014)	<p>RCT</p> <p>CG: usual care</p> <p>IG: delivery of educational interv. on CRC & CRC screening by specific pop.</p> <p>DV: 1) KAB on CRC, risk factors, & screenings 2) Intention to participate in CRC screening in the future</p>	<p>N = 654</p> <p>CG: n = 325</p> <p>IG: n = 329</p> <p>IC: aged 50-75</p> <p>Setting: Metropolitan areas in Portland, Oregon</p>	<p>Survey instruments</p>	<p>Majority of parti. were women with high school education and few taken college or technical school courses.</p> <p>Most parti. were unemployed, had health insurance, and spoke their native languages at home.</p> <p><i>Perceived behavior control and intentions</i>; the Chinese subgroup had the most impact from interv. (Control [-0.16] & interv. [0.11], $P = 0.004$). <i>Behavioral on CRC screening</i>; ([-0.06] & [0.24], $P = 0.0001$), <i>Attitudes towards behaviors</i>; ([-0.24] & [0.25], $P \leq 0.001$).</p> <p>Intentions to stay up-to-date for CRC screening were increased in Chinese and Vietnamese group, but not statistically significant.</p>	<p>The researchers concluded that an educational program delivered by trained educators using appropriate languages could impact KAB in Asian subpopulations.</p> <p>Lack of PCP or access to healthcare might influence the responses.</p> <p>Theory of Planned Behavior was a framework.</p> <p>Possible that Chinese subgroup had higher scores on certain domains due to their values on health.</p> <p>Pre & posttest baseline were lower in Korean subgroup might be due to prioritizing work over health.</p>

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To test effectiveness of telephone-based tailored education (TE) and motivational interviews (MI) in increasing CRC screening completion rate comparing to usual care (UC) (Menon, 2011).	RCT IV: TE, MI, & US DV: adherence to CRC screening through, FOBT, FIT, colono., & SIG	N = 515 Arm 1 (UC): n = 169 Arm 2 (TE): n = 168 Arm 3 (MI): n = 178 IC: age \geq 50, no hx of CRC, & being-non-adherent to stools test, colono., or SIG Setting: 2 large Midwestern medical centers & 1 Southeastern medical center.	The completion of CRC screening via SIG, colonos., or stool tests within the first 12 months post-interv.	Both TE & MI have higher CRC screening rate compares to UC. TE group has a highest screening rate (23.8 %, $P < 0.02$) & 2.2 times more likely to complete the CRC screening. TE is not significantly more effective than MI. Demographic characteristics such as genders, age, race/ethnicity/ education were not significant predictors in this study.	72% of the samples were African-Americans. Patients might not be following up after the interv. at the primary care clinic; therefore, reducing the rate of CRC screening completion. All CRC screening needs orders or referral from providers, so if patients not making another visit to follow-up they will not be able to complete the screening. Note: The health belief model & transtheoretical model of change were used as frameworks.
To compare the effectiveness of FIT outreach and colono. outreach to improve screening participation rates in comparison to usual visit-based care with at least 1 year of post interv. f/up (Singal et al., 2015).	Quantitative, Double-blinded RCT IV: mailed outreach invitations for CRC screening, FIT, colono. , unusual care, f/up telephone calls for repeat invitation	N = 5,999 Arm 1 (usual care): n = 1,199 Arm 2 (FIT): n = 2,400 Arm 3 (colono. outreach): n = 2,400 IC: aged 50- 64	Querying electronic health system laboratory data for FIT testing and a combination of test orders and administrative claims data for sigmoidoscopy or colono.	Screening participation rates were higher for FIT outreach (58.8%) and colono. outreach (42.4%) than usual care (29.6%) ($P < 0.001$ for both). FIT outreach had a higher participation rate than colono. outreach ($P < 0.001$). FIT outreach had a higher	Mailed outreach invitations for CRC screening seem to improve the CRC screening rates in underserved pop. The results are able to generalizable due to the limitation of one healthcare setting.

Purpose (Reference)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
	DV: time-to-response to FIT & colono. outreach,	years, not up-to-date with CRC screening but used primary care services in a large safety-net health system		percentage of pts. who responded before reminders (59.0% vs 29.7%; $P < 0.001$).	Pts may have received CRC screening outside the constitution.
	CRC screening rates	Setting: Dallas County		Nearly one-half of pts in the colono. outreach group crossed over to complete FIT via usual care, whereas <5% of patients in the FIT outreach group underwent usual-care colono.	There was percentage of pts who received mail invitations that were unable to contact via phone call. Note: This study identified methods to help improve CRC screening in underserved pop.

Note. AMSTAR = a measurement tool to assess systematic reviews, ARD = absolute rate difference, CI = confidence interval, Colono. = colonoscopy, CRC = colorectal cancer, DV = dependent variable, ELSA = English longitudinal of ageing, FIT = fecal immunochemical test, SIG = flexible sigmoidoscopy, F/up = follow up, FOBT = immunological fecal occult blood testing, HR = hazard ratio, Interv. = intervention, IV = independent variable, KAB = knowledge, attitudes, & beliefs, KQ = key question, NOS = newcastle ottawa scales NORCCAP = norwegian colorectal cancer prevention trial, OR = odd ratio, parti. = participants, PCP = primary care provider, pop. = population Pts = patients, QUADAS = quality assessment of diagnostic accuracy, RCT = randomized control trial, VS = versus